

Content Based Record Label Classification for Electronic Music

Georges Naimeh

Supervisors: Perfecto Herrera and Minz Won

Master Thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

September 2020
Barcelona

Copyright ©2020 by Georges S. Naimeh
Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

When God created Man, he gave him Music as a language different from all other languages. And early man sang his glory in the wilderness; and drew the hearts of kings and moved them from their thrones.

Gibran Khalil Gibran

A painter paints pictures on canvas. But musicians paint their pictures on silence.

Leopold Stokowski

If I were not a physicist, I would probably be a musician. I often think in music. I live my daydreams in music. I see my life in terms of music.

Albert Einstein

Acknowledgements

I do not know where to even begin for thanking all the people involved that has led the greatest opportunity to cross my path to get enrolled in the Sound and Music Computing program at the Music Technology Group in Universitat Pompeu Fabra.

I want to start by thanking the program coordinator Xavier Serra, who has been a mentor to me and to us all at the SMC masters, throughout all this special year filled with challenges and difficulties. I want to thank him as well, for giving me the opportunity to join the incredible Music Technology Group.

Perfecto Herrera, whose advice and hard work have always been a great source of inspiration for me, earns my deepest gratitude and respect for being an amazing friend, teacher, and most importantly one of the most sterling supervisors one can ask for. I also want to thank many other members of the MTG, especially Minz Won, who has taken care of guiding me through this research, and illuminating me with brilliant ideas.

I want to thank my partners of the SMC Master Jorge Bustos, Miguel Perrez and Igansi Nou, for helping me out whenever I got stuck in my python skills, and for being there to push me to learn every day. They have now become part of my family.

Last but not least, I could never thank enough my life partner Pamela Chami for trusting and believing in me, for what my family and friends have done for me, giving me complete support to follow my dreams. Without all of them this amazing year would not have been possible.

Abstract

Characterizing record labels and their sound signatures is a difficult problem, especially when it comes to indie record labels. That's the present when dealing with record labels of electronic music, so the application of different constructs and techniques that have been proved useful when looking at record labels is essential. On top of that Electronic music increases the challenges in similar issues, as timbre and rhythm are more important than root keys, chords, which are facets traditionally emphasized in music information retrieval. The research presented in this dissertation aims at the exploration of the usage of Music Information Retrieval tools and techniques for the analysis of Electronic Music Record Label based on audio content. For that purpose we have curated a music collection especially addressed for the above-mentioned problems, containing more than 3000 tracks of 9 different Electronic Music Record Label. The collection has been analyzed with the help of Essentia's library, and the extracted features present various musical criteria such as timbre, rhythm, and tonality. The extracted features are tested with different classification algorithms, from the simplest of them, a Support Vector Machine, to a Fully Connected layer network, to a more complex one, a Convolutional Neural Network. We also propose various ways of segmenting Electronic Music, in order to capture the most relevant features. We tried to cover as much types of segments as we can, which were tested experimentally, achieving satisfactory results. Finally, a detailed qualitative analysis of the results obtained when considering a group of record labels is performed, demonstrating the potential of the analysis that have been developed.

Keywords: *Electronic Music, Record Label, Music Classification, Audio Analysis, Excerpts Analysis, Support Vector Machine, Fully Connected Layer, Convolutional Neural Network*

List of Figures

2.1	Major Record Labels Hierarchy	10
3.1	Data	24
3.2	Features	28
3.3	Rhythm.bpm vs Pitch Saliency	29
3.4	Features Normalization	30
3.5	Cross-Validation Chart	33
3.6	Fully Connected Layer Network Architecture	34
3.7	ConvNet Architecture	36
4.1	Position of Maximum Peak of Energy	41
4.2	Position of Maximum Amplitude Envelope	42
4.3	Position of Maximum RMSe	43
4.4	120s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with SVM	44
4.5	60s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with SVM	44
4.6	30s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with SVM	45
4.7	120s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with FCL	46
4.8	60s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with FCL	47
4.9	30s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with FCL	48
4.10	Confusion Matrix for Full Tracks	51
4.11	Confusion Matrix for Adjusted Excerpts	53
4.12	Confusion Matrix for 120 seconds Chunks	54
4.13	Confusion Matrix for 60 seconds Chunks	55
4.14	Confusion Matrix for 30 seconds Chunks	57
4.15	Accuracy Plot for full tracks	59
4.16	Loss Function Plot for full tracks	59
4.17	Accuracy Plot for adjusted excerpt	60
4.18	Loss Function Plot for adjusted excerpt	60
4.19	Accuracy Plot for 120s excerpt	60
4.20	Loss Function Plot for 120s excerpt	60

4.21 Accuracy Plot for 60s excerpt	61
4.22 Loss Function Plot for 60s excerpt	61
4.23 Accuracy Plot for 30s excerpt	61
4.24 Loss Function Plot for 30s excerpt	61
4.25 FCL vs SVM Barplot Comparison	62
4.26 ConvNet Confusion Matrix for Full Tracks	63
4.27 ConvNet Confusion Matrix for 60s Balanced	64
4.28 ConvNet Confusion Matrix for 60s Unbalanced	65

List of Tables

3.1	Duration of Audio Data	24
3.2	Adaptive Excerpts over classes	31
3.3	Absolute Excerpts and Full Tracks	32
4.1	Metrics for Full Tracks	50
4.2	Metrics for Adjusted Excerpts	52
4.3	Metrics for 120 seconds chunks	54
4.4	Metrics for 60 seconds chunks	56
4.5	SVM Results with full tracks and excerpts	58
4.6	FCL Results with Full tracks and Excerpts	62
4.7	Unbalanced Excerpts per Record Label for ConvNet	65
4.8	ConvNet approaches comparison	65

Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	State of the Art	9
2.1	Electronic Music Record Labels	12
2.1.1	The Current Soundscape of Electronic Music .	12
2.1.2	Records Labels and their Aesthetics Decisions	12
2.2	Music similarity in Electronic Music Sub-genres . . .	15
2.2.1	Audio-based similarity	15
2.2.2	Non Audio-based similarity	16
2.3	Music classification in the context of Electronic Music	18
2.3.1	Genre and Sub-Genre classification	18
2.3.2	Artist classification	19
2.4	Research Question and Open Issues	20
2.5	Conclusion	20
3	Methodology	22
3.1	Classes and data set selection	22
3.1.1	Artist and Album Effect	24
3.1.2	Excerpts Analysis and Selection	25
3.2	Computational Methods Proposal	27
3.2.1	Data Pre-Processing	27
3.2.2	Computational Models	32
4	Results and Discussion	39
4.1	Excerpts Study	39
4.1.1	Absolute Excerpts	39
4.1.2	Excerpts Comparison	41
4.1.3	Fully Connected Layers	46
4.1.4	Conclusion	49

4.2	Ideal Excerpts & Full Tracks Approach	50
4.2.1	SVM Results	50
4.2.2	Fully Connected Layer Results	58
4.2.3	ConvNet Results and Discussion	63
4.2.4	Conclusion	65
5	Conclusion	67
5.1	Challenges	67
5.2	Summary	69
5.3	Future Works	69

Chapter 1

Introduction

The rise of digital music started with various emerging technologies and factors since the 1980's, like the invention of the 'MP3' file format in 1992 which was originally developed in the the early 80s by researcher Karlheinz Brandenburg. Many stimuli have played big roles in increasing the popularity of digital music like the original 'Napster' platform, which was designed to allow peer-to-peer sharing of 'MP3' files between its users in the year 2000, or Steve Jobs's Ipod invention [3]. New notions and concepts, related to music and personalization started popping out. Tremendous personalized digital audio libraries, have shrunk down into a polyvalent pocket-sized machine. Streaming Platforms, like Spotify, Deezer, Pandora, ITunes Music, Netflix to name a few, are shining with the innovations they made in the context of recommendation systems and personalization in the digital era [6]. Yet, there's always a need to improve recommendations, for instance, you can now find a playlist on most of the streaming platforms, that fits your mood in the exact moment you are choosing it. The ease of having specifically tailored content for you has made big giants like Facebook, Google and Apple, put more weights in their research departments tackling new improved technologies in that field. The trend regarding personalized content is picking up more and more, as we can see it in Ads now, posts, articles and news. Now as a musician and an electronic music producer, it came to my understanding through out the years, what an upcoming producer faces as challenges to create and release his music. Alternatively, I recently was introduced to platforms like labelradar.com and hello-demo.com where the artists like myself can

be connected to a record label. You can connect with your record label of choice if they exist on this platform of course.

The main motivation of this thesis is studying newly created music by means of automation with music information retrieval tools, by means of analyzing their acoustic and musical features, and see how they can be linked to a compatible record label that fits the sound signature. We will start by detailing the background of Electronic Music Record Labels (EMRL) in Chapter 2. We will be discussing Electronic Music and how recent Record Labels (RL) are correlated with it, in with various detailed sections. Section 2.1 will adopt the current soundscape of EM and we tackle Record Labels of Electronic Music and their workflow especially in the age of social media, new technologies, digital distributions and streaming services, not to forget their relation with an artist or a producer of the same sub-genre of EM. Section 2.2 will be dedicated to explain more about what is that EMRLs are facing nowadays, specifically in their music similarity and diversification, on audio-based and non audio-based similarity. Following that, section 2.3, will be addressing music classification in the context of EM while mentioning genre classification in EM and on another hand artist classification. Last but not least, we will tackle in Section 2.4 the open issues with the classification task we are trying to perform, and our research question.

Afterwards, in the third chapter, subdivided into two parts where we will pitch into related previous works addressing EM (Electronic Music) classification and the common ground with our classification subject here. Section 3.1, would contain an detailed explanation on our data set of choice. Most importantly, in section 3.2, we shall convey the evaluation of different audio features for the Record Label classification in our case. We shall take into account the computational methods used and the different ways of analyzing those features in order to overview our record label-fitting classification. Moreover, attributes like 'low level stats' and 'tonal level stats' shall be taken into consideration in order to extract valuable features. The effectiveness of all those features and attributes is evaluated using a Machine Learning algorithm as Support Vector Machine (SVM) and in parallel on a later stage employing Deep Learning Methods as Deep Neural Networks (DNN) to improve our classification task, which will be presented in chapter 4 as results

and discussion. We will finish up this research with chapter 5, where we discuss our results, the challenges faced, and potential works for the future.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

To start things with, we shall introduce and define Electronic Music Record Labels and Electronic Music (EM) for a clearer interpretation of our analysis regarding our classification in function of RL. In order to make sense of the essential concepts that are necessary to understand the work frame of this thesis, the target of this state of the art is to shed light on Electronic Music Genres, sub-genres and Indie Record Labels associated with EM. Additionally, clarifying the aim of this research and the problem that we will tackle.

Let us establish what Record Labels are at first and what do they do. Record labels are companies that market recorded music and corresponding videos. They engage in a wide range of functions in the music industry, including new artist recruitment and development, music publishing, and copyright enforcement. Throughout the 20th century, record labels were the dominant force behind the most successful artists. Record labels had the power to make or break artists, depending on the amount of money they invested in promoting their music [12].

Nowadays, the internet has freed artists from dependence on record labels, where many talents market and distribute their music independently through media and streaming platforms at a considerably lower rate.

One might ask now, what is the contrast between major Record Labels and Independent ones? Major or International record labels are large companies often under the control of a corporate umbrella called a “music group.” They operate their own distribution and publishing companies. This kind of RLs are also heavily funded,

they have big financial budgets for marketing, production, touring, and more. They also have a large network of connections and influences in the music industry. The big three major record labels are Sony Music Entertainment, Universal Music Group, and Warner Music Group. All other major record labels are “sub-labels” owned by either of the big three. [8] We identify next a small diagram that represents major record labels internal organizational structure.

Figure 2.1: Major Record Labels Hierarchy

On another hand, Independent record labels are small companies called indie or boutique labels. They are generally not affiliated with or funded by the three major records labels. Indie labels work with other smaller companies for distribution and publishing. Their Hierarchical Diagram doesn't exist since the Founder of the RL can be also doing the A&R work. Many consider boutique and indie labels as artist-friendly. They also offer many other benefits that may be more important to the artist. However, they don't have the funding for artists that major labels can provide but some try to push them in all means. Indie labels and boutiques generally have the advantage here. They have smaller artist rosters, which means you will get more attention. It also makes it easier to develop personal relationships and work closely with the label's team. It's always nice to work with someone who has earned your trust outside of business concerns. In contrast, most major labels have large artist rosters and so many moving parts that it can be hard to know who's working on your release. Across the board, boutique deals will tend to be more favorable to artists. Indie label contracts are known to be artist-friendly, as they tend to give artists a larger royalty percentage than major labels. For example, deals with indie record labels have trended towards simple contracts that offer 50/50 splits. This agreement gives the idea that it's a partnership of equals. Major label deals, on the other hand, rarely offer a percentage higher than 18%. There are also plenty of deductions and a level of complexity that requires the help of a lawyer to understand [27]. Furthermore, indie label contracts often give the artist most of the creative control over their music. The agreement terms also give the artist back the "ownership rights" to their music after a short period. The fact is that both types of record labels whether big or small, receive walloping amounts of demos that they can't process due to the limitations of humans hours. That is one of the incentives that made us embark on this classification task at first, but then that can have many commercial uses in more developed stage.

2.1 Electronic Music Record Labels

2.1.1 The Current Soundscape of Electronic Music

In the twentieth century, the electrification of musical instruments changed the boundaries of music. Guitar, bass, keyboards, drum machine etc. were taking different directions in their designs to ride the wave of electrification. Analog synthesizers were born and expanded the musical sound palette [25]. In the midst of ongoing changes and fast progress in these types of instruments, electronic music was yet not defined, even till our recent days. In the search of a formal definition of Electronic Music, *The Origins of Electronic Music from the Cambridge Companion to Electronic Music* entails that EM started with the invention of new Electronic Instruments [16], where the first instrument was born in 1899 called the Singing Arc invented by William Duddell. Andrew Hugill states in his paper [16] that Electronic Music is a synthesis of many different aspects that makes EM what it is: acousmatic situation, creation of new electronic instruments, the exploration of novel tuning and timbres, the use of recording and reproduction technologies, the relationship between science, mathematics and music.

Ishkur's guide ¹ give us another definition for electronic music, it states: "The first ever published electronic music depends on what your definition of an electronic music song is. The origins of electronic music go back to before it was even music and no one really kept any good records at the time (probably because of the war). Currently the earliest tracks on this guide are from 1937 but there are earlier examples of Theremin concertos which, while electronic, I would not classify as Experimental because the Theremin did a really good job pretending to not be electronic (in expert hands it could resemble a violin). That's just not avant-garde enough to be Experimental".

2.1.2 Records Labels and their Aesthetics Decisions

For the past couple of decades Record Labels have been a medium between the artists and their crowd. Following what was mentioned in *Music in Electronic Markets: An Empirical Study* [18], Record

¹<https://music.ishkur.com/>

Labels Companies (RLC) engage their business in the following activities:

- Sourcing new talent;
- Producing recordings;
- Manufacturing a physical product (e.g. vinyl, tape, CD);

And another set of activities that falls out of our scope that is not paramount to list. Although we have to add on the list above, that recent technologies and innovations in this industry have made RLs operate in a more efficient way where this will be more developed in the next section to follow, especially, a big portion of the EM genre, that is considered more or less a niche of indie record labels where each promote their own genre or style, considered to a certain extent as the identity of the record label itself.

RLs in the past had only one product to sell which was vinyls. Today, a bunch of services and products are available for the marketing team to spread the identity of the labels, whether it was a physical product or digital. Although, to follow with the new trends of streaming services (ie. Spotify, Deezer, Soundcloud) and most importantly digital releases (ie. mp3, wav) presented in an Extended Play (EP) catalog form or a Various Artists (VA) compilation, Record Labels, more specifically EMRLs, put into service a list of digital distributors (ie. proton, ampsuite) and digital stores (ie. beatport, traxsource, junodownload, bandcamp). On another hand, one of the activities that RLs used to do is scout for new artists and talent to sign on the label as mentioned in [18]. Recently, EMRLS switched to the digital realm and tend to lookout for upcoming talents on digital platforms like Bandcamp or Soundcloud. Subsequently, they also tend to receive a lot of demos from producers or musicians by using services like 'labelradar.com' or 'hello-demo.com'. While globalisation is inevitable with all the tech innovations we are witnessing, EMRLs are receiving huge amounts of demos from artists all over the world, to the point where the need for a team to filter out this data is unavoidable and inevitable. Yet, no budget is or will get allocated for that. This usually falls under the scope of the Artist and Relation position in the label, where one will find himself overwhelmed to be doing this kind of tasks manually. Based on a recent interview done by one of the prestigious electronic music magazines called "When We Dip" [9], Patrick Bruyndonx² explains more about

²<https://www.residentadvisor.net/news/43979>

his vision for his record label called "SoukSonic". The interviewer from When We Dip asks him the following question: What's your criteria for signing music ? Do you have a specific genre/sound that you envision for the new label ? Patrick aka Lost Desert replies: "Well, I like to think I do, but then you get a great track that's different and all plans go out the window. But there is a vision ! In my mind at least, if I can draw a blue print with a few words they would be... WOULD BE: Ethnic, original, melodic, melancholic, organic, groovy, sexy WOULD NOT BE: Too lounge or too banging, full melodies and vocal movie samples, tech, proggy, straight, snare rolls and white noises, cold, big room One thing I would like to say to young (and old) producers out there !! A kick, hi hat and a clap with a default Synth Pad is not a "All Day I Dream" or "Souksonic" track. It takes more than that, I want to hear passion, emotion, detail, and originality. Something I can remember (and not from another track). Try writing original melodies and vocal lines, record original sounds and voices. When I hear that in a track, you have a good shot, even when the sound is not perfect at that time". This gives us a small insight on how indie EMRLs attack their scouting quest for new sounds to sign for their RL. Following the latter, we can notice as well that "Lost Desert" used text-based descriptors and annotations to discern the kind of music he is looking for to sign to his label. We will dive into this in details in the next sections to come. On another hand, based on the fact that I work as A&R for Bar25 Record Label based in Berlin, I planned a small interview with the CEO, Danny Faber, asking him few questions that will give us another insight for how does RLs operate. After asking him what are the ways Record Labels make decisions about signing artists or tracks, he replied clearly: Strategy, Reach and Quality of music, where underlined in his intervention. He explained that they circulate the potential release first on all team members, distributors, marketing specialists in the music biz, they even test it out in DJ sets. They distribute it to close friends and established artists to play it in clubs, festivals etc. and try to record the feedback of the crowd on it. This helps a lot in decisions of release or not as from this move the track can mostly explain itself. He also added that they try to diversify the offer in terms of tackling different sub-genres, by creating compilation products following a genre, a target or create new sub-labels with specific genre direction. When asked

about sticking to well-known names and consolidated styles or considering publishing different and unfashionable stylometric music he affirmed that beside the established artists they have on the roster, they try to support as much as possible newcomers while giving them at least a 10% of the full catalog of releases per year.

2.2 Music similarity in Electronic Music Sub-genres

Music similarity at its core is very likely to be a subjective perception and context dependant as cited by Pampalk [22]. Similar aspects of characteristics like timbre, melody, rhythm and tempo help define related music to others.

We are still in an era where a machine cannot replace humans. This means it won't be able to define or interpret similarity on audio based samples as users perceive given all the information that are compressed in a track. That in itself has made it difficult for music computation tasks to be handled, narrower over Electronic Music.

2.2.1 Audio-based similarity

Music similarity computed from the audio signal can be put in playlist generation, recommendation of new music or artists, or even classification of music collections. Impractically, music similarity is very complex, multi-dimensional and context-dependent [23]. Defining algorithms which model the perception of similarity would require extensive listening tests. Another way to tackle this is to evaluate the performance of genre classification. The hypothesis is that similar music belong to the same genre. Despite that music genres taxonomies are different this assumption holds. Moreover, music genres are a conventional concept to classify large music collections.

Electronic Music similarity based on audio-content is also defined by the analysis of the content-based information existing, from temporal signature and timbral identities as major factors. Nonetheless, many dimensions of music have been shown to be relatively paramount to use as a baseline: tempo, rhythm, voice qualities, etc. as mentioned in [2]. Audio-based electronic music similarity focuses on more than one particularly important dimensions. Thus acknowledging that, make us realize that improving our classification onto

record label can always be improved, similarly to other works done in the past [23]. Nonetheless, we ought to mention that indie record labels have a tendency to follow independent conventional guidelines to sign or release new music. C.Strachan argues that the motivations that drives indie and micro record labels are totally different from the big companies of music like Universal, Warner Bros etc. [27]. He also adds that indie record labels shift their processes of signing new music dependently on how well you are connected in the scene that follows your style. Most importantly he defends that a record label style or sound identity is equal to its owner. He interviewed Nigel Tuner owner of Pickled Eggs founded in 1998 which released mostly playful art-house pop and indie rock music:

‘What Turner understands as his own ‘personal taste’ may be read by others within the scene as the label’s ‘ethos’, ‘agenda’ or distinct identity.’ mentions Stratchan [27].

From this point onward, we can somehow say that the latter can imply onto our targeted indie electronic music record labels, since this shows a cohesion and homogeneity in their sounds. Even though, a record label will want to release something out of the box once and that might not follow the usual conventional trend of the sound it presents to its followers. Nevertheless, a style of the record label has many factors as the one stated earlier, so naturally each micro record label have more probability following a sound identity rather than different genres. As a result, we can carry on our research with the sole of keeping in mind that our targeted EMRLs are conventionally coherent with their musical direction.

In the next paragraph, we will be talking about non-audio based content.

2.2.2 Non Audio-based similarity

The recent progress of Electronic Music creates a natural pressure for fine-grained musical metadata. The metadata in question is used to give music streaming services which are able to cope with the mere size of music catalogues, and the desire of users to access music titles by similarity. In the relatively new field of Music Information Retrieval, various systems have been developed that classify music according to a certain type of similarity. A majority of research work done in this field focuses on classification of broader genres, but not the multitude of sub-genres contained within them. This

number is large when it comes to the domain of electronic music, and this calls for a necessary sub-division within the genre. Initially, most of the genre classification approaches relied on non-audio based content, and not on the actual audio [26]. Entirely metadata-based methods of similarity judgements have to make use of metadata applied by human annotators or automated music tagging algorithms. Text-based metadata related to audio builds a big part in the non audio-based similarity space. Moreover, describing terms like album name, artist name, cover, remix, year, key of the track, bpm, mood, feeling and more can all be considered substantial metadata for recommendation systems using co-occurrence matrices [30]. However, this metadata introduce a new problem of its own. Detailed music taxonomy by an annotator takes a good amount of time, taxonomy labels can only be applied to known examples, and it can be difficult to achieve a conventional taxonomy on music description, even amongst expert listeners as West [29] mentioned. Nonetheless, non-audio based electronic music similarity would entail the taxonomy used to describe those tracks without relying on the content and the analysis of the audio file itself. Taxonomy categories like 'mood, instruments, feel, tempo, danceability, vocals ...' and a lot more annotations would be used to arrange any collection, thus classifying Electronic Music based on non-audio based content would be helpful for our classification task here as well with the merge of audio-based electronic music similarity. Although when it comes to sub-genres of Electronic Music what we aim for mostly in those taxonomies, is creating a sort of a latent space where clusters following this metadata, can be formed automatically. For example having 2 tracks that have same annotations considering the mood as 'dreamy', similar instruments as well like 'pads, strings', can be seen grouped together in the same cluster. While having different tempo signature, they can be close to each other in this space.

Most importantly for our classification endeavor the most ideal non audio-based descriptors or metadata, that we need to consider, can be based on the following criteria: bpm, key, instruments, mood or feel. Where the latter can be extracted from raw audio data. This list of text-based descriptors can be considered for future works for annotating our data set that will help us more with our classification. We felt the necessity mentioning this approach in order to clear out the spectrum of features that we ought to deal with.

2.3 Music classification in the context of Electronic Music

According to Fu et al [13] the main engagements in Music Classification are Genre Classification, Mood Classification, Artist Identification, Instrument Recognition and Music Annotation. Genre classification is the one that turned the whole community hyped about it. In this context Aucouturier et Pachet [2] show that genre is an ambiguous term, it is not founded in any intrinsic property of the music, but rather relies on cultural extrinsic habits. Nevertheless, it is proved that it is one of the most practical notions to distinguish music. Listeners usually narrate music in terms of its genre, so an automatic system for identifying similarities in Genre, Artists, Albums, especially Record Labels is potentially very useful.

2.3.1 Genre and Sub-Genre classification

The uniqueness of electronic/dance music in the 90s has produced a meta-genre that is ceaselessly growing, recombining, and creating superannuated numerous sub-genres on a yearly basis [20]. Mcleod et al [20] , also states that there is no single overriding factor that has given rise to this situation. Instead, the naming of new sub-genres can be linked to a variety of influences, such as the rapidly evolving nature of the music, accelerated consumer culture, and the synergy created by record company marketing strategies and music magazine hype [4]. Musical genres are not just labels applied to music, rather they seem to exist both at a private level, as cognitive types, and as socialized nuclear content that is as socialized sets of instructions to detect occurrences of types. One of the attempts to define a genre is as follows: A genre is a kind of music, which is acknowledged by the community for any reason or purpose or criteria. [10]

The first problem that occurs is that there are no exact boundaries between different genres. In addition, there are many combinations and "hybrid" genres that make different genres or sub-genres often overlapping and therefore in turn makes the genre distinction often a nontrivial endeavour. Kirss in his masters thesis [17] addresses the classification task of electronic music excerpts in a five-genre taxonomy: Ambient, Deep House, Uplifting, Trance,

Techno and Drum-and-Bass. At that time, that was a novel piece of research. He constructs an in-house data set of 250 songs and extracts a number of timbral and rhythmic audio features from different tools. Afterwards he invests those features in training several different Machine Learning Algorithms. He checks various combinations of features and algorithms, and determines that the best result is obtained when using timbral and rhythmic features from Rhythm Patterns¹ and Marsyas² toolboxes to train a Support Vector Machine. The accuracy reached with this combination is above 96 percent in 10-fold cross-validation. On another hand, it is worth mentioning that accuracy as a result and comparative reference by no means covers the full spectrum of available methods for genre classification due to the vast amount of work done in this area. We should not omit as well, that the size of the data set used is a paramount factor not to be tolerated, as if too small may result in most cases with over-fitting of the model. Moreover, the results should be treated with caution due to variations in implementation details even for the same features used. For instance, in [14] and [19] where different number of features was used in two different approaches and network architectures, and they both lead to different results, depending on the features taken into consideration.

2.3.2 Artist classification

The specific task of identifying the artist or in other terms producer, with an Electronic Music data set, has been tackled so far by Melidis [21]. He uses an in-house data set comprised of 5949 songs corresponding to 111 artists of different sub-genres, from which 86 are finally used. For each artist 5 albums are collected, dedicating three of them to train the system and the other two for testing. A series of descriptors from different toolboxes are computed from 30-seconds excerpts corresponding to the second half of the first minute of each song. From MIRToolbox⁵ a number of Dynamics, Rhythm, Timbre, Pitch and Tonal descriptors are computed, while from Essentia only Spectral Energy, the MFCC coefficients and the HPCPs are obtained. He also calculates Zipf-based descriptors for MFCCs, Loudness and HPCPs invested in different machine learning models that yielded with different accuracies based on several factors. The main picture here, is that each artist will differ with the identity of his releases, thus not all of his music will be similar, yet there's

an identity to each artist or producer with his sound signature, but that doesn't mean that all the music that the artist produces will be similar.

2.4 Research Question and Open Issues

The most common issues we will be facing is actually the similarity in the music we are classifying, as we are looking in catalogs of Indie Record Labels of EM that tackles specific genre of music. In this thesis, the issues rely in conveying to the machine that each Record Label has a specific sound signature for it. Moreover, we will be tackling the problem of discerning the sound of a label by whether an entry in question should be classified in a specific RL. The fact is that we will be using dissimilar music between the classes to a certain extent, still electronic, but different in terms of text-based similarity. As a result, the main challenge that yet needs to be tackled is whether current State-of-the-Art in Music Information Retrieval techniques are able to classify similar music into their respective Electronic Music Record Labels.

2.5 Conclusion

Music Information Retrieval, as a discipline, has a developed series of tools and techniques that have a great potential for analyzing music, more particularly, Electronic Music. For that reason, we consider this study as an investigation of the potential of technological tools for the classification of electronic music in record labels.

In this development we will be addressing the following goals:

- Explore the potential of MIR tools and techniques for the classification task.

- Determine which audio features best capture the style of the record label.

- Test the ability of those audio features to discriminate between record labels.

The gap between record labels and producers tend to be closed, recently more than ever. With recent technologies like social media platforms, streaming services and MIR tools, we believe that we are in the right moment to try making the 'record label-producer' relation more fluid, for both parties involved, and most importantly

personalized. However, we might happen to meet with MIR tools to not perfectly fit with our classification. In that case, a clarification of the method evolved should be presented. We hope the results obtained while developing this thesis will allow us to improve our understanding of Electronic Music, as well as being useful for tasks such as recommendations systems and filters. We trust that it will be an ultimatum and an opportunity to seize and discover the capabilities of MIR tools and techniques in different scenarios.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter we will be addressing the classes, data set selection, algorithms and neural networks architectures to be used and the methodology adopted in the process. Over this context, we will report the main methodological steps performed, starting in Section 3.1 from gathering all the data set of the electronic music sub genres and the choice of classes made. In section 3.2 we will talk about the architecture of our models and the features used. At last, the output of all our experiments will be, therefore, a label indicating the class in which the new observation is more likely to belong according to the computed model. The final step is to determine the performance of the system. The most usual way is to compute some Figures of merit, such as Precision, Recall, Accuracy, F-Measure and so on, obtained from the comparison between the predicted class and a baseline. Recently, Urbano et Al [28] published a paper arguing for a more formalized evaluation or even a new approach that focuses more on the musical meaningfulness of the individual classifications than the determination of a numerical overall measure. He states that every batch evaluation in the Information Retrieval field follows the Cranfield Paradigm which uses several effectiveness measures to score systems following different criteria.

3.1 Classes and data set selection

Music Information Retrieval tasks are challenging due to the music collection that we would like to gather for the expansion of the analysis and results acquired. An investigation like the one developed

here undeniably requires a very specific data set that is challenging to collect. We will be presenting an in-house data set made through out years of gathering catalogs of Electronic Music genres and sub-genres. We then take into consideration the most relevant aspects of the data to keep all the information well organized. The group of sets was chosen based on personal collections that met our requirements while trying to diversify and cover the Electronic Music Universe which we discussed earlier in chapter 2. While keeping this in mind, we considered genres and sub-genres like Techno for Kompakt and Stil Vor Talent, House for Bar25 and LittleHelpers, Disco for Defected, Tech House for Suara, Broken Techno for Mord, Experimental for Ninja Tune. Chill-out and instrumental hip-hop for Chillhop. Since the labels we named are established record labels that has been in the industry for almost 10 years, we know that we can take advantage of their backlog catalog, due to the amount of data that they acquired through out the years of releasing music. This implies then, that each record label shall be considered as a class to be discerned by the frameworks we will adopt. Finally we explain the process that has been emphasized on for choosing which record labels are to be analyzed. The choice of the classes, RLS in our case, was made while keeping it with a considerable amount of variance in function of the sub-genre to genre ratio. In order to discern some similarity in the style of the record labels a ratio of similarity was taken conventionally based on some factors like taxonomies, duration of tracks, instruments, bpm. Meaning a record label like Mord records was paramount to consider as dissimilar data for our classification task. Nonetheless, record labels like Kompakt and Suara follow some how the same direction together with Bar25 and StilVorTalent. The record labels that are intended to be used are: Bar25, Defected Records, Chillhop Records, Kompakt, MORD, Ninja Tune, Stil Vor Talent, Suara, Little Helpers.

Thoroughly, we ought to present some stats that reflects the type of our data, which describes the distribution of our entries for every class, and the total duration of every record label, and the total duration of all our dataset:

Figure 3.1: Data

Record Label	Tracks	Total Duration of Data
Kompakt	329	66 hours 40 minutes 31 seconds
Little Helpers	360	40 hours 36 minutes 50 seconds
Chillhop	333	15 hours 37 minutes 19 seconds
Suara	571	66 hours 40 minutes 31 seconds
Bar 25	422	52 hours 24 minutes 32 seconds
Mord	406	38 hours 43 minutes 34 seconds
Stilvortalent	580	66 hours 34 minutes 44 seconds
Defected	1560	234 hours 2 minutes 47 seconds
Ninja Tune	305	23 hours 42 minutes 3 seconds
Total	4866	577 hours 24 minutes 30 seconds

Table 3.1: Duration of Audio Data

3.1.1 Artist and Album Effect

To ensure reliability of the accuracy results, only recordings by artists different from the ones present in the training data are used in the test data. The album and artist effect play a big role in biasing the outcome we look up for. The fact is that, in case of the presence of one track of an artist from an album in the training set, and another one from the same album and the same artist in the test set. [11]. What we want is a classifier that minimizes any bias on specific artists and captures a blend of many of them as represented by a given label. The artist and album effect filter is a way to minimize such potential bias to artists in the learning of a supracategory that engulfs them (record label). Due to the latter, we performed a manual filtering through our database of around 2700 tracks in order to ensure that our data set is not contaminated and is good to work with.

3.1.2 Excerpts Analysis and Selection

In order to tackle different approaches by trying to discover the best path to achieve this research, we embarked on an unconventional approach of considering excerpts of electronic music that are considered representatives of our tracks in the dataset. What we want to achieve is to know, up to which degree can we consider our results, conditioned by segments extracted from our audio tracks, which in turn would allow us to share the contents and data of our music collection without being restricted by copyright issues, and would allow less computational times. What we want to reach as a result is to identify a potential candidate to represent our electronic music track. A candidate where length and position are the its core characteristics.

Fixed area of excerpts or absolute excerpts

In order to conduct other experiments that we must emphasize on, chunking our tracks into different chunk sizes is a paramount step to prepare our data prior to our computations. The chunking approach was inspired as a continuity from a previous Masters Thesis in UPF,Barcelona, that discussed Audio-Based Computational Stylometry for Electronic Music [1]. This direction will help us discover up to which degree while considering excerpts can we maximize the performance of our classifier in question, by taking into account different metrics like the F1-score, precision, recall and accuracy.

Following that, we define our chunks respectively from full tracks length, 2 minutes, 1 minute, to even 30 seconds. We created a python script that allowed us to slice our tracks with a specified number of seconds, and export them into a new directory. This tool is posted on Github publicly¹. We also discarded all the chunks that are smaller than the specified length in each experiment, respectively.

We will calculate for every length of excerpt the energy peak position, the amplitude envelope maximum position and the maximum root mean squared energy (RMSe) position. The maximum amplitude envelope being the smooth curve of the envelope outlining the extremes and the RMSe, where for audio signals, that roughly corresponds to the root mean squared of how loud the signal is.

¹<https://github.com/Gnai/Audio-Chunking-Tool>

Subsequently, chunks were created with the audio-chunking-tool created specifically for this, and were named respectively with the name of the track ending with 'c{x}', where x being the order of chunk from the beginning of the track depending on the chunk size that we are experimenting with. An example might illustrate this better; let's consider a track from "Mord" record label called "Charlton - Face Recognition (Original Mix)". This track is about 6 minutes and 20 seconds long: for a 1 minute chunk length logically this should generate 6 chunks while the last 20 seconds are discarded. File names should be as following:

- Charlton - Face Recognition (Original Mix)-c0
- Charlton - Face Recognition (Original Mix)-c1
- Charlton - Face Recognition (Original Mix)-c2
- Charlton - Face Recognition (Original Mix)-c3
- Charlton - Face Recognition (Original Mix)-c4
- Charlton - Face Recognition (Original Mix)-c5

With this layout of chunks our choice would be between c2 and c3. For consistency, it is very important to adopt a common method that helps us decide between c2 and c3, with all chunk sizes from all tracks for our experiments. Counting all "c2"s and "c3"s of all the classes, we ought to pick the highest number of chunks that can be generated for all record labels. Specifically, over this case of chunk length of 1 minute, our chunk choice would be "c2" as this will generate the biggest quantity of chunked data.

Adaptive Position for Excerpts

Another approach of chunk selection that we should discuss and not ignore is the approach of an energy adaptive chunk, where we shall define it as the excerpt that includes the energy peak in the middle. In order to take into consideration also all the chunks which their energy peak might be located outside of our 40-60 zone, we decided to adopt a direction to consider them as well, since they can count as well as a potential representation for the track in question. For this we have built a script with python that finds the energy peak of the track which slice from one side and from another respectively 15 seconds, 30 seconds and 60 seconds. That will result in chunks of 30seconds, 60 seconds and 120 seconds, where the energy peak in question will be in the middle of the track. Although the process of extracting a specifically-located segment from might affect the

information pulled from our data, this might help us prove that we could consider one chunk of a track only, where the energy peak exists, whether it is the smallest chunk or another one. We will discuss the results in chapter 4. That being said we shall gather a balanced data set for all our classes which we will mention in parallel with the other approaches, to compare carefully and fairly, and where we shall run it with an experiment in chapter 4.

The 40-60 Adjusted Excerpts

In this section we will describe more the type of chunk chosen here and why it is important to take it into consideration as well. This type of excerpts is extracted from the 40% of the track till 60% of the track, respectively. Which means, that automatically every excerpt will have a different length but taken from the same position. For this we have used Essentia's embedded function, the MonoLoader² that helped us segment our tracks as a sample based approach this time, by loading the raw audio data from an audio file and downmixing it to mono. It is paramount to try and explore different possibilities in an experiment. What this one will yield, is an assertive definition of whether we should always consider this kind of adjusted excerpts.

3.2 Computational Methods Proposal

3.2.1 Data Pre-Processing

After putting together an adequate data set, the next stage is to extract a set of features that captures specific characteristics of the music. This step is the more challenging of all, as determining which descriptors should be computed in order to separate observations belonging to different classes is not a trivial task at all. The number of available descriptors in the literature is increasingly high, and cover from the lowest level of abstraction (raw numbers extracted directly from the source, easily interpretative by a machine but meaningless for humans) to the highest level of abstraction (semantic descriptions easily understandable by humans but extremely complex for machines). They also represent most of the facets of music: Rhythm,

²https://essentia.upf.edu/reference/std_MonoLoader.html

Pitch, Timbre, Melody, Harmony, etc. The success of the classification procedure strongly depends on the features chosen, so one could argue that it is one of the most crucial parts in the process chain.

However, the increasing computational capacity of nowadays machines has allowed many researchers to compute tremendous models of data and focus on improving other aspects of the system. Instead, on another hand, making efforts in building better features for getting closer to the way we humans perceive music. A usual step for avoiding having to deal with a large number of features is performing a dimensional reduction technique, such as feature selection. The way in which we profit of the extracted features depends on the learning approach that we use. The most common one is supervised learning, meaning that observations are used to train a machine learning model which will build a model that will allow it to perform some predictions regarding the class to which another observation belongs.

We will adopt all levels features as an input for all models, like it was done earlier by previous authors and works [24]. Features like BPM, track key, energy of the track and average loudness, to name a few, will be considered.

The table below shows an example of the data extracted from all our data as full tracks or chunks:

average_loudness	barkbands_crest.mean	barkbands_crest.stdev	barkbands_flatness_db.mean	barkbands_flatness_db.stdev	barkbands_kurtosis.mean
0.926209	13.066208	6.341759	0.191187	0.084679	25.695114
0.801614	12.663761	6.788875	0.196887	0.120882	68.848587
0.958840	15.589139	6.508586	0.194571	0.095030	29.897995
0.959844	16.034716	5.544224	0.186143	0.103511	63.320503
0.921126	14.520344	5.613762	0.258785	0.145858	43.360104

Figure 3.2: Features

We thought it would be interesting to plot one of the features to have a better visualization of the distribution of our data features. As we can see in Fig.3.3 we can notice that a big batch of our data lies around the 120 beats-per-minute(bpm) which characterizes electronic dance music. We also notice that some labels like 'chillhop' and 'ninjatune' falls out of the 120 bpm zone, which creates a sort

of coverage for the bpm characteristic.

Figure 3.3: Rhythm.bpm vs Pitch Saliency

After extracting all features from all chunks, normalization is an important step before training our model. Normalization is the process of scaling individual samples to achieve uniformity. Here's an example of pre-processed normalized data:

	average_loudness	barkbands_crest.mean	barkbands_crest.stdev	barkbands_flatness_db.mean	barkbands_flatness_db.stdev	barkbands_kurtosis.mean
count	2745.000000	2745.000000	2745.000000	2745.000000	2745.000000	2745.000000
mean	0.878187	0.548738	0.607527	0.348608	0.406127	0.077189
std	0.166332	0.132811	0.137274	0.144951	0.138441	0.070362
min	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
25%	0.865440	0.459425	0.517212	0.246496	0.312587	0.031530
50%	0.940132	0.544800	0.613359	0.333757	0.395170	0.059855
75%	0.971751	0.634478	0.707315	0.435052	0.490542	0.099724
max	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000	1.000000

Figure 3.4: Features Normalization

Typical machine learning algorithms for supervised learning are k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN), Decision Trees, Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and many more. In our task we will be using different combinations of architectures but we will underline and focus on Support Vector Machines, Deep Neural Network using Keras and a convolutional neural network with Pytorch, since they showed efficiency in the results of their performances with music classification tasks [23], [14], [13], [31], we will talk more about our computational models in section 3.2.2.

When performing a supervised machine learning experiment it is a common practice to hold on our validation data in order to avoid over-fitting, and contamination. The most widely used split ratio is 70% for training and 30% for validating or 80% by 20%. We will opt for the 80 to 20 train-validation split with the help an in-built function of the sci-kit learn.

The tables below show us how are data is divided following our excerpts sizes after applying the artist and album effect filter, while we can notice that our data is not perfectly balanced considering different chunk sizes for the only reason that some of our tracks in the data set can be less than 120, 60 and 30 seconds, where chunks less than the amount specified are discarded, so tracks that are for example 75 seconds would be cropped into one chunk with the rest of 15 seconds discarded and so on and so forth.

Record Label	120s Excerpts	60s Excerpts	30s Excerpts
Kompakt	249	304	323
Little Helpers	282	326	341
Chillhop	115	265	315
Suara	387	482	522
Bar 25	317	366	385
Mord	245	315	353
Stilvortalent	482	550	575
Defected	519	574	588
Ninja Tune	177	241	283
Total	2773	3423	3985

Table 3.2: Adaptive Excerpts over classes

With the table below we can see how our train/validation split is made and what is the quantity of data that is generated by using the absolute excerpts this time with the full tracks.

	Full Tracks&Adjusted	120s	60s Balanced	60s Unbalanced	30s
Train(0.8)	2196	2066	2088	2971	2138
Test(0.2)	549	517	522	742	535

Table 3.3: Absolute Excerpts and Full Tracks

3.2.2 Computational Models

Support Vector Machine

Support vector machine, are widely used algorithms in classification tasks, as we mentioned earlier. Adopting this direction of framework of multi-class classification as a machine learning one, showed interesting results in different experiments [17]. Support vector machines (SVMs) have shown superb performance in classification tasks[32]. The basic idea is to transform input vectors into a high-dimensional feature space using non-linear transformation, and then to do a linear separation in feature space. In other words, SVM aims at searching for a hyper-plane that separates the positive data points to the negative ones with maximum margin. To extend SVMs for multi-class classification, we use one-versus-all approach, pairwise comparison, and multi-class objective functions [33].

We will be starting off with this model at first and experimenting with all chunk sizes recursively. A uniformity and consistency should be set as a baseline to try out the model with different sizes of chunks, which will allow us to compare what approach of chunk sizes is best for this machine learning framework. After extracting the features from the data, and having them in a comma separated value file, a conventional guideline is to split this data into training and validation data.

The common SVM model we used for all chunks, have the gamma parameters set to range between 0.001 and 1, with a cross-validation factor of 10. We are using sklearn’s library for SVM models which opts for GridSearchCV module and allows us to fit,predict and score. Here is a flowchart of our typical cross validation workflow for our model training:

Fully Connected Layers

Fully connected layers are the most primitive form of a convolutional neural network. A ConvNet is composed of multiple layers of

Figure 3.5: Cross-Validation Chart

artificial neurons. Artificial neurons, a rough imitation of their biological counterparts, but representing mathematical functions that calculate the weighted sum of multiple inputs and outputs as an activation value, we will dive in more details about ConvNet in the next subsection. In spite of the fact that pure fully-connected networks are the simplest type of networks, understanding the principles of their work is useful for many reasons. Fully connected layer networks and ConvNets, are identified with forward propagation and backward propagation of computations. Forward pass is basically a set of operations which transform network input into the output space. During the inference stage neural network relies solely on the forward pass. The architecture of our fully connected layer was achieved using Keras sequential model, which is an API designed to make deep learning approaches easier and faster to write and setup. With Keras we opted for the sequential model³ which defines an input to output model path. There's not a standardized form for fixing the number of neurons in a layer, or even the number and type of layer that might exist in this network. It all depends on the functionality of the model being built and for which function will it serve. After trial and error for our multi-label classification task we adopted a 110 neurons as the first hidden layer which includes after that a batch normalization layer that serves to normalize the input layer by re-centering and re-scaling. Following the latter, we shall use a 'tanh' activation function as widely used in classification

³https://keras.io/guides/sequential_model/

tasks. As for the second hidden layer, it is quite similar to the previous one with 50 neurons instead of 110, and a 'Relu' activation function. 'ReLU' is a non-linear activation function that is used in multi-layer neural networks. This function can be represented as: $f(x) = \max(0, x)$, where x =input value. The 'ReLU' function is able to accelerate the training speed of deep neural networks compared to traditional activation functions. We have to point out the fact that our output layer neurons shall be defined exactly equal to the number of existing classes in the classification task; in our case 9 Record Labels. Followed by a 'Softmax' activation function, which is a common activation function for our classification task. However, a summary of our fully connected layer is shown below:

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
InputLayer (BatchNormalizati	(None, 110)	440
HiddenLayer_1 (Dense)	(None, 110)	12210
batch_normalization_13 (Batc	(None, 110)	440
activation_19 (Activation)	(None, 110)	0
dropout_13 (Dropout)	(None, 110)	0
HiddenLayer_2 (Dense)	(None, 50)	5550
batch_normalization_14 (Batc	(None, 50)	200
activation_20 (Activation)	(None, 50)	0
dropout_14 (Dropout)	(None, 50)	0
Output_layer (Dense)	(None, 9)	459
activation_21 (Activation)	(None, 9)	0
Total params: 19,299		
Trainable params: 18,759		
Non-trainable params: 540		

Figure 3.6: Fully Connected Layer Network Architecture

Nevertheless, coming back to our topic about back-prop and after getting that output, it might need to be updated in function of the weights. That's where back propagation comes in handy as an algorithm which calculates error gradients with respect to each network variable (neuron weights and biases). Those gradients are later used in optimization algorithms, such as Gradient Descent, which updates them correspondingly. The process of weights and biases update is called Backward Pass. In favor of calculating error gradients, we have to start by computing the loss function. Luckily, Keras has already a built in function which does that automatically. To make this work in Keras we need to compile the model so that an important choice to take is the loss function. We use the categorical cross-entropy loss and not the usual binary cross-entropy loss in classification due to the fact that we are aiming here for a multi-class classification and not a multi-label classification. This might seem unreasonable, but we want to penalize each output node dependently. So we pick a categorical loss coupled with a 'softmax' layer as the output layer. For the ease of building a network with Keras, it also has an embedded functionality that may call an optimizer of your choice depending on the task to serve. In our case, we picked out the 'Adam' optimizer which is the most common and the most recommended for classification tasks with a batch size of 50, and 50 vs 100 epochs. We will be discussing all results in the next chapter of this thesis, tackling as stated earlier different sizes of chunks and full tracks as well, just like we operated our machine learning framework.

Convolutional Neural Network

Fully connected networks with a few layers can only do so much – to get close to state-of-the-art results in any classification it is necessary to go deeper, by using a Convolutional Neural Network (ConvNet). Although we won't be going into deep details about the specific choice of the architecture of the network designed, we will talk about paramount factors that are considered crucial to run the network smoothly with Pytorch, a library designed to ease the process of building a ConvNet. The architecture of our network is a state-of-the-art one that engages with automatic music tagging inspired by previous work [31]. It includes 5 layers of convolutions where each one of them has a batch normalization one and a max

pooling one to follow. Our output layer shall be a 'Softmax' one since we are engaging in a classification task. Below you can see the order of our architecture in more details:

Operational Layer		Number filters	Kernel
Input Spectrum		-	-
Convolutional Layer (Layer 1)	Convolution Batch Norm ELU	64	3 x 3
Pooling Layer	Max Pooling	1	2 x 4
Convolutional Layer (Layer 2)	Convolution Batch Norm ELU	128	3 x 3
Pooling Layer	Max Pooling	1	2 x 4
Convolutional Layer (Layer 3)	Convolution Batch Norm ELU	128	3 x 3
Pooling Layer	Max Pooling	1	2 x 4
Convolutional Layer (Layer 4)	Convolution Batch Norm ELU	128	3 x 3
Pooling Layer	Max Pooling	1	3 x 5
Convolutional Layer (Layer 5)	Convolution Batch Norm ELU	64	3 x 3
Pooling Layer	Max Pooling	1	4 x 4
Pooling Layer	Average Pooling	1	<i>1 x chunk from previous layer</i>
Inner Product	Fully Connected Layer	-	-

Figure 3.7: ConvNet Architecture

As ConvNets function differently than fully connected layers as a deep learning framework, we want to try different experiments with this approach in order to minimize our computational cost, in terms of time and GPU resources. First, we will adopt a 1 minute chunk only, considered from the climax of the tracks resulting in a balanced data of 290 chunks for each label, in order to compare that with the previous algorithms, to see if a ConvNet can actually give us better results and if it makes sense considering other chunk sizes. From another perspective, we will take all 1 minute chunks from the whole tracks, so we would consider a chunked-version of a full track, resulting in an imbalanced data set, which can benefit us due to the amount of data we will gather. We shall apply the inverted distribution weight approach on the imbalanced set. In parallel, we will perform the same experiment with the imbalanced dataset but without the inverted weight distribution in order to grasp the importance of that method, and if it really affects our results. Our last experiment involves a balanced full-tracks data set to test our ConvNet with 240 tracks for each class, which is also conducted in order for us to see if ConvNets would really level up the game. In ConvNets, technical notions like weights regularization and initialization, have to be mentioned especially in an experiment where our

data set is an imbalanced one.

Regularization significantly reduces the variance of the model, without substantial increase in its bias. In other non-technical terms, it is a useful technique that can help in improving the accuracy of our regression model while avoiding over-fitting. In our case we implemented regularization by using the Dropout embedded functionality with Pytorch, in the classifier layer.

Weights initialization strategy was first explored and addressed in the influential work of Glorot et al [15]. It derives an appropriate range of uniform distribution for each layer. This distribution is used to sample the weights for the network initialization. It commonly goes by the name Xavier's initialization. We implemented that function with the ease of Pytorch language, while initiating the network with it's learning rate, loss function and our choice of optimizer. Those aforementioned parameters are considered hyper ones that need tuning depending on the performance of our ConvNet. Naturally, a learning rate alpha should be decreased manually or automatically with the number of epochs, depending on the loss function. Our choice of optimizer, depends highly on the task and the approach we are taking for this task. The most commonly used optimizer is the "Adam" one. As for the loss function, the choice of this is critical regarding the experiment with imbalanced data set, due to the fact that we need to compensate for the classes that are down-sampled. There's more than one method to engage in this action of setting up weights depending if a class is down-sampled or up-sampled. The best practice for weights is to use the inverse of the label distribution. In our imbalanced data set for example, one class like "Defected Records" has 2215 1-minute chunk samples versus another class like "Chillhop" has 577 samples. Logically, the class that has higher number of samples will be given a smaller weight, where in parallel the class that has a small number of samples will be given a higher weight. For this experiment only we define a variable called class_weights and implement it as an argument in cross entropy loss function, which should solve our problem of weighing our imbalanced classes. Although we use the same cross entropy loss function from Pytorch for the 2 other balanced data set experiments, we should omit the approach of weighing our classes as it might confuse our network and it won't make sense. We present and discuss the results in the next chapter for all experiments done

with our ConvNet.

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

In this chapter we analyze the results gathered from the previous experiments and connect them with explanations and interpretations. For this matter, we have decided first to discuss and report what we presented in section 3.1.2, since that will allow us to adopt the ideal excerpt choice for the continuation of this research. We have decided to take into account the study for the optimal determination of an excerpt as length in time duration and the perfect position for this that we achieved, so that we can consider it as a full track representative. We will then compare the best excerpt candidate and the full electronic music track of each label, and what the classifiers produced as performance results. Last but not least, we shall discuss as well, the performances of our classifiers, and whether a complex classifier might have an upper hand in this type of classification task, compared to simpler ones.

4.1 Excerpts Study

In this section we shall tackle the choice of excerpts and their results, and at the same time compare one to another in order to find out who is the ideal candidate to be considered as a representative for our tracks.

4.1.1 Absolute Excerpts

Based on this, the excerpt choice will be a selective and meticulous process. We chose our chunks to be located in the middle of the track . The reason behind this approach is the fact that commonly

any electronic track is conventionally structured to include all instruments, vocals or percussion in between this frame. In electronic music that window where everything happens is called a climax or the 'IT' [7], which fortifies our choice of this specific piece of chunk segmented from all tracks for our experiments.

In order to discover our choice of chunk location in the latter case, we conducted an experiment where we calculated the position of, the energy peak level using 'Essentia', maximum amplitude envelope position, and maximum RMSe position, using the 'Librosa' library. All of this was conducted for all tracks in our data set in order to support our chunk choice selection. Although there's a lot of variations in the boxes, we can still consider that the average of the positions for all record labels comes in between 40% to 60% as the Energy peak box-plot below shows:

One can argue though, that the energy peak metric as a measure do not necessarily represent the ideal metric to base our chunk choice on, since Loudness is a measure that considers a longer time window, not just using an instantaneous value like the energy peak. It is also perceptually motivated, and could be a more robust and less dispersed feature to capture the idea of the "climax". Due to that, we shall consider two more metrics in order to back up our choice of chunks position. For that we calculated the maximum amplitude envelope position, and the maximum RMSe position that are showed in the following box-plots:

After plotting, the values we have, we look at the global average of both metrics, where the mean for the position of maximum RMSe is 40.44% and the mean of the position of the maximum amplitude envelope is 44.27%, adding to that the mean of the position of the maximum energy peak which is 51.66% . Consequently, a chunk that has all 3 positions in the 40% to 60% area will be a choice that we can consider. This is why we can consider the absolute excerpt that falls in between 40 and 60% as a potential candidate. In order to be more assertive on the last statement in the next section, we shall consider as well, an approach where the chunk length is adapted depending solely on the position of the energy peak, and compare those two methods to see which one is yielding better results.

Figure 4.1: Position of Maximum Peak of Energy

4.1.2 Excerpts Comparison

In this section we will discuss the results that our experiment yielded from the energy adaptive chunk, where for each track we cropped the segment where the energy peak comes exactly in the middle, and compare it with a sister excerpt from the absolute chunk family.

SVM Results

For this experiment, we adopted the adaptive chunk sizes to compare with the absolute ones. Both chunked data should have the same number of slices in order to present the most fair comparison. Which is 115 track per record label, in order to keep everything

Figure 4.2: Position of Maximum Amplitude Envelope

balanced and present one excerpt, and one only, from each track. We followed a set of fixed hyper-parameters using a support vector machine algorithm.

120 Seconds Excerpts On one hand, we start with the two minute excerpt length, we plot the f1-score that yielded from the adaptive excerpt based on the energy peak, where the latter comes in the middle of the chunk, pairing it with the absolute excerpt f1-score results. For the purpose of a fair comparison we have to use the same number of chunks for both approaches:

In the above results, we can see that the absolute segments of audio provided a better accuracy which is actually 56.5%, compared to

Figure 4.3: Position of Maximum RMSe

the part where we have our segments that includes the energy peak only which yielded in a 54.1%. More importantly, we can notice that 'chillhop', 'bar25', 'mord' have the highest values in f1-score, which translates to a better predictions on those labels. 'chillhop' has the highest f1-score value probably because their excerpts represents the whole track, since audio data in this RL are usually of 2 to 3 minutes long. In counter parts, 'bar25' and 'stilvortalent' for example, didn't yield good results with their classification, as we can analyze from the f1-score compared to other labels. We also grasp that the absolute excerpts performed in general better in the f1-score values for 5 RLs out of 9.

Figure 4.4: 120s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with SVM

60 seconds Excerpts Recursively, we shall use the same direction that we followed earlier to compare in a similar way the 60 seconds adaptive excerpts over the absolute ones. We shall fix the same parameters used in the previous experiments for this one as well.

Figure 4.5: 60s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with SVM

In the 60 seconds excerpts case 'chillhop' and 'littlehelpers' have the highest f1-scores. The accuracy for this experiment was at 52.6% for the adaptive path compared to 53.1%. We can also conclude from here that absolute excerpt path is performing better than its sister the adaptive. We notice as well that the accuracy metric dropped down compared to the 120s excerpts, which probably means that the longer the duration the better. 'littlehelpers' is a RL that represents minimal house music, and what is a bit ambiguous is that it actually scored a good measure for the f1 metric that might be probably due to a fact that it always kept the same sound for almost a decade.

30 seconds Excerpts The last part of the SVM direction experiments ends with the 30 seconds excerpts. We can notice in fig.4.6 that 'chillhop' has always the highest f1-score metric.

Figure 4.6: 30s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with SVM

As we mentioned earlier, that the tracks from this RL, are actually short in length, what makes the fact that from these 3 excerpts that we considered they could all represent an entire track somehow for this label. The accuracy of the adaptive is at 46.8% compared to 51.2% for the absolute excerpt approach. One, can also not help to notice that 'suara' is the least well classified between those RLs, due to the fact that 'suara', and it is known for a fast beat electronic music RL, has changed a lot the style they are releasing from the beginning of the label till present times.

Conclusion

From all the experiment above we can conclude that we can account for the absolute excerpt candidate, as it showed better results than the other family member, the adaptive chunk. As we can notice as well that our accuracy metric as well as the weighted f1-score metric have decreased with the duration of the excerpts. Which raises our curiosity to tackle similar MIR classification tasks with different approaches, which we will mention in chapter 5 of this study.

4.1.3 Fully Connected Layers

120 seconds excerpts At this stage, we shall present the same guideline that we followed earlier but with the fully connected layer method. For this we shall look as well for our bar plots in function of the f1-score to rule out which excerpt type can be a good candidate for that.

Figure 4.7: 120s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with FCL

Comparing both approaches, again with the same number of excerpts for both directions, we can observe that 'chillhop' is still being classified the best between all of our classes. However, 'mord' from the adaptive excerpt type, is doing better than most of the tracks, contrarily to 'stilvortalent' and 'bar25' that have the lowest f1-score, which might be due to a genre similarity between those 2 record labels. And we can notice as well that 'littlehelpers' have the same

f1-score whatever the chunk type is, which probably is due for the fact that both excerpts for this specific case are capturing the same important information. For the 120seconds excerpts we can observe that the absolute candidate has better results for the f1-score for 6 RLs out of 9, which justifies the reported accuracy to be at 60.86% for the absolute versus a 56.03% for the adaptive. Which puts the absolute excerpt candidate in a good position to be an ideal representative for this path.

60 seconds excerpts In this paragraph we shall observe the results of the adaptive excerpt candidate and the absolute one, in a fully connected layer framework.

Figure 4.8: 60s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with FCL

We can review the f1-score for both type of excerpts for all the classes in fig.4.8. We criticize 'stilvortalent' label which has the almost the same f1-score for both candidates. Nevertheless, we can only notice that 5 out of 9 RL have higher f1-scores for the absolute chunk, what is translated in the accuracy metric with 52.1% for the adaptive chunk and 55.0% for the absolute one.

30 seconds excerpts Let us resume at the end with the 30 seconds excerpts. Where in this section we have to observe what results are yielding from this length of excerpts.

Figure 4.9: 30s Adaptive vs Absolute Excerpts with FCL

We can clearly notice from the bar plot in fig.4.9, that the adaptive chunk in this case exceptionally have better results than the absolute. The accuracy for the adaptive excerpt is 53.6% compared to 49.7% for the absolute excerpt. Which is translated in the 6 out of 9 RL having higher f1-scores than the absolute approach. We pay attention to 'littlehelpers' as well that is close to 'chillhop' now, which is probably due to the fact that this RL has a unique sound.

4.1.4 Conclusion

From those results we can conclude that for the 30 seconds excerpts we have the highest F1-score for the adaptive excerpts compared in the FCL approach, which is justifiable by the fact that the categorical excerpts might contain some silence, while they are picked in a zone known as the climax. And since in electronic music, what comes before the climax is a kind of a silence to prepare for the 'break', the categorical excerpts could have been just before that peak, with the peak not included in the excerpt. However, and for all the other approaches we shall go with the absolute excerpt candidate since it showed better results. What we can notice at least is that with the simplicity of the SVM framework we mostly figured out what was the better candidate for this task, without needing really to adopt a more complex approach like our fully connected layer here, since the improvement here was kind of modest for most of the directions.

4.2 Ideal Excerpts & Full Tracks Approach

In this section we conduct different experiments comparing chunk sizes with different algorithms adopted, from taking into account simple algorithms like the SVM to a more complex one like a ConvNet. We shall conduct our experiments with the absolute excerpt type that is the best candidate for this and add as well the adjusted one which comes in different lengths but exactly extracted between the 40 and 60% of each track individually. It is paramount to underline the fact that each track has one excerpt to represent it, and one excerpt only.

4.2.1 SVM Results

Full Tracks

We started our approach with the simple path of considering the model with our full tracks. The audio tracks as it, no chunks are considered for this method. Using a machine learning algorithm yielded logical results that we are going to interpret with a cause-and-effect reasoning. After running our model through our data of full tracks that resulted in different merit scores:

Table 4.1: Metrics for Full Tracks

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Bar25	0.46	0.56	0.50	57
ChillHop	0.82	0.87	0.85	54
Defected	0.60	0.69	0.64	65
Kompakt	0.55	0.42	0.48	64
LittleHelpers	0.79	0.80	0.80	66
Mord	0.82	0.91	0.86	70
NinjaTune	0.53	0.48	0.50	60
StilVorTalent	0.51	0.52	0.51	50
Suara	0.51	0.38	0.44	63
accuracy			0.63	549
macro avg	0.62	0.63	0.62	549
weighted avg	0.63	0.63	0.63	549

The metric scores for each class, more specifically the f1-score and recall are the highest for 'Mord' which backs up what we have interpreted previously from our confusion matrix. Since the data set

is balanced we can use the accuracy as well as a metric, where the value is not actually far from other metrics and lies down at 63.20%. We can comment this score is considerably low compared to other frameworks in general, which is normal, as classifying audio-content based on Indie Record Labels in Electronic Music is not an easy task with a support vector machine algorithm. We shall pursue a comparison in the next results of experiments to discern how this approach will engage with different sizes of chunks taken from the climax of our tracks.

Figure 4.10: Confusion Matrix for Full Tracks

From this matrix we can deduce some arguments that can help us understand our model more; with this direction of using full tracks, we notice that our model has clearly classified 'Mord' better than other classes, and wrongly predicted 13 'Kompakt' tracks into 'NinjaTune'. This might be due to the reason that some of 'Kompakt' tracks are similar to 'NinjaTune'. By similar we mean that they might be close with the tempo, key selection, timbral features and other aspects. If we scan through the matrix in question, we can notice this pattern with different predictions as well, like another example, 12 tracks from 'Suara' were predicted in 'Defected', and so on and so forth. The fact is that in Electronic Music, Indie Record Labels can intertwine with some releases, with some low to high level features. Thus a machine learning algorithm might not yet be able to discern the differences. Other metric measures that backs up our interpretation above can be illustrated below with f1-score, precision metric, recall and support:

Adjusted Excerpts

In this section we provide the results that we conducted on our experiments of the adjusted excerpts with the SVM, in order for us to see which is the best representative for our study. We have to underline the fact, that this excerpt comes exactly from 40% to 60% in the track while neglecting the energy peak and ignoring other criteria.

Table 4.2: Metrics for Adjusted Excerpts

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Bar25	0.46	0.59	0.52	64
ChillHop	0.81	0.87	0.84	54
Defected	0.52	0.56	0.54	50
Kompakt	0.41	0.28	0.33	57
LittleHelpers	0.75	0.75	0.75	65
Mord	0.71	0.79	0.75	70
NinjaTune	0.58	0.48	0.53	66
StilVorTalent	0.40	0.43	0.42	60
Suara	0.43	0.37	0.39	63
accuracy			0.57	549
macro avg	0.56	0.57	0.56	549
weighted avg	0.57	0.57	0.57	549

We can comment that 'chillhop', 'mord' and 'littlehelpers' has the highest f1-score here, and 'kompakt' has the lowest as well which might resulting from the fact that 'kompakt' which is a RL known for long duration tracks and diversified techno sound doesn't allow this category of excerpts to be as fairly representative as it can be.

Figure 4.11: Confusion Matrix for Adjusted Excerpts

We can also observe on the confusion above in fig.4.11, and see the translation of the above metrics into this classification metrics, 'mord' and 'chillhop' have the highest numbers of True Positives, and 'kompakt' has the least one. This experiment has resulted with an accuracy of 57.1%

120 seconds chunks

As mentioned earlier, we shall experiment with absolute excerpts of 120 seconds. We use the same baseline used previously in the above model for full tracks. After compiling our model with the features extracted from our chunks we result with the following metrics:

Table 4.3: Metrics for 120 seconds chunks

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Bar25	0.44	0.55	0.49	55
ChillHop	0.78	0.94	0.85	53
Defected	0.55	0.60	0.57	57
Kompakt	0.64	0.48	0.55	52
LittleHelpers	0.70	0.83	0.76	54
Mord	0.76	0.85	0.80	65
NinjaTune	0.59	0.33	0.43	57
StilVorTalent	0.55	0.52	0.54	63
Suara	0.57	0.52	0.55	61
accuracy			0.62	517
macro avg	0.62	0.63	0.62	517
weighted avg	0.62	0.62	0.62	517

Figure 4.12: Confusion Matrix for 120 seconds Chunks

From the confusion matrix and the table above, we can notice that our model is predicting 'Mord' the best, but compared to the full tracks confusion matrix, our model this time is classifying less

samples into the same class: 55 for the 120 seconds compared to 64 for the full tracks. Although the number of samples for each model is not the same, by looking at the actual row of 'Mord' we can see clearly that the model this time has more false negatives samples classified into different classes, for example, 3 samples were classified in 'Suara', in total 10 samples were classified in wrong classes compared to only 6 samples classified in the wrong classes with the full tracks model. If we follow that iterative logic through out the other classes, we can assume that the model is predicting with less accuracy due to the fact that the window size of information shrank down to 120 seconds instead of a full track. The accuracy metric for this experiment is 62.47%.

60 seconds chunks

In order to experiment with our model more we tested out 60 seconds chunks with the categorical excerpts, and got the following results below:

Figure 4.13: Confusion Matrix for 60 seconds Chunks

Table 4.4: Metrics for 60 seconds chunks

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Bar25	0.59	0.57	0.58	61
ChillHop	0.85	0.87	0.86	63
Defected	0.51	0.54	0.52	59
Kompakt	0.57	0.50	0.53	50
LittleHelpers	0.69	0.78	0.74	64
Mord	0.83	0.80	0.81	65
NinjaTune	0.45	0.40	0.42	48
StilVorTalent	0.47	0.53	0.50	53
Suara	0.35	0.32	0.34	59
accuracy			0.60	522
macro avg	0.59	0.59	0.59	522
weighted avg	0.60	0.60	0.60	522

From those results we can say that for 'Chillhop' for example, the predicted samples are higher than previous models already stated, probably because the tracks in this record label are around 1 minute to 2 minutes as a whole track duration, so while chunking the tracks here, not much of the information extracted were lost. In fact, on one hand compared to other classes has the higher metrics scores. On another hand, 'Mord' has less correctly predicted samples than the two previous models. If we also check other classes we can deduce that the prediction for the aforementioned models is better than this one, with an accuracy of 60.34%. Probably, due to the fact that the information extracted are more limited compared to bigger length of tracks. On a side note, although the number of samples for this approach were higher than the one of 120 seconds, the accuracy metric is less. With this, we can extract that even with more data the above models are performing better.

30 seconds chunks

To have a clearer conclusion on our algorithm we decided to chunk the tracks even smaller to 30 seconds but using the absolute excerpt as we proved earlier that this is the best direction for this length. We must also mention that we are using here 2547 excerpts, all extracted from the middle of the track while taking into consideration the criteria we mentioned in section 4.1.1.

From this we can derive that 'Chillhop' is the best predicted class

Figure 4.14: Confusion Matrix for 30 seconds Chunks

for the fact that we stated earlier. One thing to note, 30 seconds of chunks our model is not performing as we expect it to be for the other classes. While the accuracy is 49.5%, it explains that with this chunk size, our features extracted are not enough to have a substantial accuracy in a machine learning framework.

Conclusion

Machine learning is a powerful tool if used correctly, in simpler classifications tasks, it only requires a CPU and needs less data. As for our case here, we can see that having a full track sample is the optimal case for our model to perform at it's best. While having to compute and extract the features from this data, full tracks samples is computationally more expensive as it would need more time to lay on the features, where as for 120 seconds and 60 seconds, the time extract those features are far less. The substantial compromise we would have to do is the accuracy of prediction. For the full tracks we waited around 3 days to get our information extracted from the audio compared to 1 day for the 120s and couple of hours for the others. In a research context, that might not be a big problematic but for a commercial endeavor that is considered as a time gap if that task is a blocker. In the table 4.5 we can see the compared results with the type of excerpts.

Table 4.5: SVM Results with full tracks and excerpts

	Full Tracks	Adj.Exc.	120s	60s	30s
F1-Score	0.63	0.57	0.62	0.60	0.59
Precision	0.62	0.56	0.62	0.60	0.58
Recall	0.63	0.57	0.63	0.59	0.58
Accuracy	63.20%	57.19%	62.47%	60.34%	58.6%

4.2.2 Fully Connected Layer Results

As we conducted our first group of experiments with a machine learning approach, we shall do the same for the deep learning framework. The same reasoning shall be followed for this path as well, by looking at loss functions and accuracy graphs, will definitely be more informative for us to draw a conclusion of how our model is performing. While engaging in the first experiment of full track samples, we should mention the reason behind the architecture of our model. In the previous chapter, we detailed the structure of our neural net by stating that it includes 110 neurons as a first hidden layer, then 55 and then 9 naturally for the output layer. As a matter of fact, before settling over this structure of network we tried different architectures, like for example 90, 40, to 9, where this experiment yielded in a 67.21% accuracy and a weighted f1-score of 0.67, and for 45, 20, 9, we got a 66% accuracy. Regardless of the accuracy metric we got, the reason why we chose the 110, 55, 9 structure is due to the fact that after training and validating our model, we engaged to test this model only on new unseen, independent data from each label. Tracks that are newly released or to be released soon. So in other words, our model never saw this data. We gathered 10 tracks from each RL, extracted the 110 features as well and then normalized it. After saving our 'Keras' model, we call the 'model.predict' function which allows us to test this new data on the model. Since we reshaped our output vectors into 'one hot vectors' our output will be a vector with different percentage for each class. So one track can match different classes, while giving the highest value to a predicted class by using the 'argmax' of the predicted vector from python. After trying different structures, the algorithm performed best with the architecture chosen and stated earlier. That is the main reason why we adopted this form for our fully connected layer and decided to use it on all of our other chunks.

Full tracks

We are taking advantage of the same extracted features data we used earlier and fed them to our neural net. Using Keras's embedded functionalities 'model.fit' and 'model.evaluate' will allow us to fit and score our training data over the predicted ones by the model. Down this line, the accuracy of this model reached a 69.03%. Even with this accuracy metric is we should check our loss function plot and our accuracy plot for the training and validation data, we can notice from the curves that our model is not over-fitting since if we check the plot of training loss decreases to a point of stability.

Figure 4.15: Accuracy Plot for full tracks

Figure 4.16: Loss Function Plot for full tracks

The plot of validation loss decreases to a point of stability and has kind of a gap with the training loss: we can predict that more training to the model in question here will result in over-fitting of the model that's why we adopted a 50 epochs standard. A good fit is identified by a training and validation loss that decreases to a point of stability with a minimal gap between the two final loss values.

The loss of the model will almost always be lower on the training data set than the validation data set. This means that we should expect some gap between the train and validation loss learning curves. This gap is referred to as the “generalization gap.”

Adjusted Excerpts

Following the same conducted experiment we did in section 4.1.1 tackling the adjusted excerpts type which was extracted and cropped exactly from the 40 to 60% of the track. This experiment has resulted with a 63.2% accuracy which is lower than the one for the

full tracks we shall compare every result at the end of the section.

Figure 4.17: Accuracy Plot for adjusted excerpt

Figure 4.18: Loss Function Plot for adjusted excerpt

From those 2 plots we can notice that the model might over fit if we trained it more than 50 epochs, as the gap at the end of the curves is getting bigger.

120 seconds chunks

On another note, testing the same architecture with 120 seconds chunk sizes was interesting, as this yielded in really similar results while using a fully connected layer network. It resulted with an accuracy of 63.82%. With the loss function and the accuracy regarding the training and validation data set, we plot both graphs below:

Figure 4.19: Accuracy Plot for 120s excerpt

Figure 4.20: Loss Function Plot for 120s excerpt

We can notice that the data is fitted normally. Let's check the results for the 60 seconds.

60 seconds chunks

Normally our accuracy should drop compared to the other sample sizes, similar to our case with the SVM. In this case, the margin is actually not that significant. It yielded an accuracy of 63.4% with the graphs shown below:

Figure 4.21: Accuracy Plot for 60s excerpt

Figure 4.22: Loss Function Plot for 60s excerpt

30 seconds chunks

As we showed in section 4.1.1. the best results that yielded for this duration of excerpts was the adaptive excerpt which was extracted depending on the energy peak conditioning it to be in the middle of our excerpt here. With the scenario of the 30 seconds excerpts, we had 2547 excerpts generated from every track. Only one chunk was cropped from every track, and one only. The margin of our accuracy is still not that substantial. It yielded an accuracy of 56.60% with the graphs shown below using the adaptive excerpts approach:

Figure 4.23: Accuracy Plot for 30s excerpt

Figure 4.24: Loss Function Plot for 30s excerpt

Conclusion

Table 4.6: FCL Results with Full tracks and Excerpts

	Full Tracks	Adj. Exc.	120s	60s	30s
F1-Score	0.690	0.63	0.63	0.63	0.56
Precision	0.69	0.62	0.63	0.62	0.57
Recall	0.69	0.63	0.64	0.63	0.56
Accuracy	69.03%	63.02%	63.82%	63.40%	56.60%

As neural networks are hungry for data more than machine learning frameworks this is what have might resulted in the increase of the accuracy compared to SVM. We can still notice though that for both frameworks, SVM and FCL, the best results are yielded with the full tracks path as we can see in table 4.6 and in fig. 4.25. We can observe as well that between the 120 seconds excerpts and the 60 seconds excerpts there's not a major margin, for the only fact that if there's less information in the 60 seconds chunks compared to the 120 seconds, the quantity of data of the 60 seconds excerpts will make up for this difference.

Figure 4.25: FCL vs SVM Barplot Comparison

One final thing to point out is the fact, that the 30 seconds excerpts performed better with the absolute excerpt in the SVM approach compared to the adaptive excerpt used in the FCL framework. Which is probably due to the fact that looking at the complexity of the FCL framework and the adaptive excerpt type, the latter approach requires more data to perform at its best.

4.2.3 ConvNet Results and Discussion

Moving to the ConvNet framework, we ought to train our network with the same data that we used earlier. Nevertheless, we thought of adding the 60 seconds unbalanced chunks, for us to be able to compare between the balanced and the unbalanced, and at the same time, compare the effect of the inverted weight distribution on our classification performance.

Full Tracks

Following our ConvNet training as we stated in the previous chapter, we can comment on the results we have translated into the confusion matrix for this baseline we adopted.

Figure 4.26: ConvNet Confusion Matrix for Full Tracks

Reading through the confusion matrix we can notice that 'Defected' and 'Suara' were the badly classified which comes from the fact that defected covers a wide range of electronic music and can jump from house to disco, tech house to techno. Since in the early days of 'Suara', this record label represented a bit of disco and house before switching completely to techno, that justifies why 10 entry from 'Defected' were classified in 'Suara'. The F1-Score for this path is 0.59 and the accuracy reaches 59.9%.

60s balanced excerpts

For this approach we adopted the categorical excerpt line. After training our neural network we can comment on the results that reached 0.60 for the F1-score and a 60.7% accuracy. From this, we deduct that 'Ninja tune' is the worst classified, and that might be due to the fact of the length of the tracks in this record label, which are generally between 3 to 4 minutes.

Figure 4.27: ConvNet Confusion Matrix for 60s Balanced

60s unbalanced excerpts

We opted for this direction in order to compare the balanced and unbalanced data training, while adding on top of that, the inverted weight distribution method and subtracting it as well. We can see in the table below the distribution of our data onto the labels, and so we can notice that Defected has a huge amount of excerpts which can be useful if used correctly:

Applying the inverted weight distribution on this, resulted with an accuracy of 61.9% and a F1-Score of 0.61. Comparing those result to another experiment we did without applying the inverted weight distribution, we received an accuracy of 34.9%. Thus, showing what the weight distribution can improve in the training of our neural network.

Record Label	No.of Chunks
Kompakt	238
Little Helpers	278
Chillhop	249
Suara	440
Bar 25	335
Mord	305
Stilvortalent	446
Defected	1188
Ninja Tune	234
Total	3713

Table 4.7: Unbalanced Excerpts per Record Label for ConvNet

Figure 4.28: ConvNet Confusion Matrix for 60s Unbalanced

4.2.4 Conclusion

Table 4.8: ConvNet approaches comparison

	Full Tracks	60s Balanced	60s Unbalanced (IDW ¹)	60s Unbalanced (IDW)
F1-Score	0.59	0.60	0.61	0.34
Precision	0.60	0.61	0.63	0.33
Recall	0.60	0.61	0.62	0.35
Accuracy	59.9%	60.7%	61.9%	34.9%
Epochs	200	200	200	200

As a conclusion we plotted all the values and metrics that our experiment with the ConvNet yielded. Surprisingly, we got the best results with the inverted weight distribution used on the unbalanced

data set of 60 seconds. Which proves that unbalanced data set can be considerate to large amounts of data when we need it for cases like ConvNets.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In order to summarize this project, in this final chapter we will argue about the challenges we encountered in the progress of this thesis. We will discuss the most relevant contributions that were discovered and suggest a few lines of investigation that may be intriguing to take from where the present research has reached. Our research study, started around creating a classification model based on audio content for electronic music record labels. The main focus here, was to find the most ideal system, with the right approach to tackle, in order to deliver a state-of-art path line that sheds light on the most efficient direction to perform this type of music classification. We took different focus points, from sizes of excerpts, and an analysis that justifies our extracted excerpt choices, to comparing them all together in order to find the ideal candidate that might make a good representative for our data. We will discuss more the results in section 5.2.

5.1 Challenges

While experimenting with this thesis we have encountered several challenges, as how to define Electronic Music for example. Till now there's no formal worldwide definition for Electronic Music. We proposed a definition which we based our research on, but similar definitions can be added to this one. Although we are positive that this is a very reasonable hypothesis, we are conscious that some of our readers, might disagree with the fact that 'Chillhop Records' is not necessarily considered in the Electronic Music genre, since it

represents the 'instrumental hip-hop' sub-genre. It is paramount to discuss the fact that the selection of the record labels comprised in this data set was meticulously picked in order to try and present different sub-genres of electronic music, so that our model can be as representative as it can get of the electronic music world. For instance, 'Ninja Tune' and 'Mord' have more experimental to broken techno kind of style, and they are on the complete opposite realm of electronic music, compared to 'Bar25' and 'Stilvortalent', characterized by a four-over-four type of music, described by a techno sound.

Another challenge to point out is the choice of algorithms and architectures adopted for this research. Nevertheless, we decided to conduct paramount experiments more closely related with the choice of excerpts for example where we have noticed that those experiments, despite having shown a high degree of coherence in the features selected, can be improved in order to fix some key points. This point will be developed more in detail in Section 5.3. Most of the challenges that prompted out during this discussion have been revealed thanks to the studies conducted in Chapter 4. However, we should be very cautious with the generalization of the methodologies that we have developed and tested, as the number of record labels we considered was extremely reduced for the sake of this research, and the features selection and the deep networks architectures might not prove to be the best.

Another bump that we faced during our research was the lack of computational power to support our ConvNet framework. Thus providing more experiments down that line was limiting due to the fact that ConvNet requires huge horsepower [5], which was only accessible for us with the use of remote services like Google Colab and the grid on campus of the UPF provided by the MTG. We ought to mention as well, that coming from an acoustic engineering background to perform this research was the most challenging for this study. We have learned hands-on skills with python, that helped us shape the way to accomplish our research. It is with the help of the MTG group, my colleagues and most importantly my supervisor, that we have succeeded in working around with the computational tools available in order to achieve this research.

5.2 Summary

Despite the challenges mentioned in the previous section, we strongly trust that this research has generated relevant contributions for the MIR community. We have shown that current state of the art MIR tools and techniques are able to capture features that characterize the works of the analyzed RLS, even though we have just scratched the surface. We resumed the work that have been previously stated in previous research to explore the path of focusing on small excerpts as well as on full tracks. That independently allowed us to navigate musical signature that identifies each label and that can only be detected on small scales, focusing on energy peaks for excerpts of 30 seconds for example. While we believe, that using a fixed size excerpts might not give the same results as the full tracks, we think that selecting the right duration of excerpts which can include the energy peak, the maximum of amplitude envelope, or even the maximum RMSe, can result in intriguing results. Although we think that the proposed baseline can be improved, we strongly believe that it has the potential to be considered a starting checkpoint for future studies.

You can find all the models, experiments and extracted features data are available within the following link: https://github.com/Gnai/record_label_classification_for_electronic_music

5.3 Future Works

In the early stages of this research, the aim of it has been mainly exploratory. Achieving reliable computational analysis for Electronic Music is a potential for various applications, like recommendation systems and expert assistance in music production. In the near future, we are keen on some characteristics that can improve the results of our research or maybe even adopt it as a path.

- Underlining the fact that a varying length of excerpts depends on the track, the genre, the sub-genres and the features extracted, might be more efficient for computational times and yield better results.

- The methodology detailed for determining the most representative features might be improved to a specific set of features that represents electronic music better.

-One can tackle every audio classification task in the 'duration' of data he acquires for the research and not by the quantity of tracks or audio files. Standardizing the process of audio-related information retrieval researches is a step towards accomplishing uniformity in this field, in order to unify all experiments. More research can be done in this area to provide a clearer idea on the data used and how it should be used.

-Stereo signal for audio analysis could have been also taken into account, and might also yield better results in all frameworks.

- Different ConvNet models architectures can result in different performances. That can be another study to tackle with this classification task while acquiring more data to feed to the neural network.

Other questions have emerged along the research that raised ambiguity, which can be a path to be adopted for future works:

-Does the "Artist Effect" have the same impact in Electronic Music as it does in "recorded" music? As we all know, that most of the producers always change their samples, instruments, and even the pre-designed sounds they can find in presets of VSTs or packs. Which in turn should result in a different style of an EP or album while even using the same techniques of production that the artist uses usually.

-Can we use the proposed techniques to track the evolution of Record Labels in Electronic Music? As we mentioned in the first chapters, that some record labels depend on their owners musical taste, so the sound of the label evolves with it's owners. In some cases we can even distinguish clearly different styles from when the RL started till the present time. It is intriguing to test if the extracted features can help detecting the style evolution of the record label.

-Can we get better results while using 2 representative excerpts from one track? We have this idea while performing our excerpt analysis, that one chunk might not be enough to represent a whole track of 6 minutes for examples. We might need 2 chunks, let's say for example: one with an energy peak and one from the start or the end of the track. That is something that can be very interesting if tackled in the right way.

We hope for the future, that the direction described earlier can be answered, which will lead to a lot of interesting conclusions, and would definitely help the community to understand and grasp the

concepts of Electronic Music, it may even lead to a formal universal definition for Electronic Music.

We feel the need to mention though, that this research analysis, came to light while pursuing an ideal system of multi-label classification in order to help music creators and producers worldwide. With their defined genres, they will be linked ideally, to a fitting record label, taking into account their sound and their signature. All of that shall be pursued beyond this research as well, while giving credit to the study itself, and everyone who was involved in this.

Bibliography

- [1] Francisco Rodriguez Algarra. audio-based computational stylometry for electronic music Francisco Rodríguez-Algarra master thesis UPF / 2014 Master in Sound and Music Computing. 2014.
- [2] Jean-julien Aucouturier and François Pachet. Music Similarity Measures : What ' s the Use ? Ismir, page 7, 2002.
- [3] Michael Bull. No dead air! The iPod and the culture of mobile listening. Leisure Studies, 24(4):343–355, 2005.
- [4] Antonio Caparrini, Javier Arroyo, Laura Pérez-Molina, and Jaime Sánchez-Hernández. Automatic subgenre classification in an electronic dance music taxonomy. Journal of New Music Research, 8215(May), 2020.
- [5] Chunlei Chen, Peng Zhang, Huixiang Zhang, Jiangyan Dai, Yugen Yi, Huihui Zhang, Yonghui Zhang, and Malik Jahan Khan. Deep Learning on Computational-Resource-Limited Platforms: A Survey. Mobile Information Systems, 2020, 2020.
- [6] Tuck Siong Chung, Roland T. Rust, and Michel Wedel. My mobile music: An adaptive personalization system for digital audio players. Marketing Science, 28(1):52–68, 2009.
- [7] David Cope. The Mechanics of Listening to Electronic Music. Music Educators Journal, 64(2):47–51, 1977.
- [8] Brian R. Day. In Defense of Copyright: Creativity, Record Labels, and the Future of Music. SSRN Electronic Journal, 2012.
- [9] When We Dip. Lost desert & simon vuarambon unveil a new collaboration on souksonic, 2020.

- [10] Franco Fabbri. Browsing Music Spaces: Categories And The Musical Mind. Education, pages 1–14, 1999.
- [11] Arthur Flexer. A closer look on artist filters for musical genre classification. Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, ISMIR 2007, (February):341–344, 2007.
- [12] Patrick Fogarty. Major record labels and the RIAA: dinosaurs in a digital age? Houston Business and Tax Journal, 1:141–174, 2008.
- [13] Zhouyu Fu, Guojun Lu, Kai Ming Ting, and Dengsheng Zhang. A survey of audio-based music classification and annotation. IEEE Transactions on Multimedia, 13(2):303–319, 2011.
- [14] Michal Genussov and Israel Cohen. Musical genre classification of audio signals using geometric methods. European Signal Processing Conference, 10(5):497–501, 2010.
- [15] Xavier Glorot and Yoshua Bengio. Understanding the difficulty of training deep feedforward neural networks. Journal of Machine Learning Research, 9:249–256, 2010.
- [16] Andrew Hugill. The Origins of Electronic Music, page 7–24. Cambridge Companions to Music. Cambridge University Press, 2 edition, 2017.
- [17] Priit Kirss. Audio Based Genre Classification of Electronic Music. Master’s thesis, 2007.
- [18] Martin Kretschmer, George Michael Klimis, and Roger Wallis. Music in electronic markets: An empirical study. New Media & Society, 3(4):417–441, 2001.
- [19] Michael I. Mandel and Daniel P.W. Ellis. Song-level features and support vector machines for music classification. ISMIR 2005 - 6th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, pages 594–599, 2005.
- [20] Kembrew McLeod. Genres, subgenres, sub-subgenres and more: Musical and social differentiation within electronic/dance music communities. Journal of Popular Music Studies, 13(1):59–75, 2001.

- [21] Panagiotis Melidis. Electronic music artist identification. Master’s thesis, UPF, 2012.
- [22] Elias Pampalk. Computational Models of Music Similarity and their Application in Music Information Retrieval. Technischen Universitat Wien, 193:165, 2006.
- [23] Elias Pampalk, Arthur Flexer, and Gerhard Widmer. Improvements of audio-based music similarity and genre classification. ISMIR 2005 - 6th International Conference on Music Information Retrieval, pages 628–633, 2005.
- [24] Zengchang Qin, Wei Liu, and Tao Wan. A Bag-of-Tones Model with MFCC Features. International Conference on Advanced Data Mining and Applications (ADMA 2013), pages 564–575, 2013.
- [25] Curtis Road. The computer music tutorial, volume 32. MIT, february 1 edition, 1996.
- [26] P. Siva Sankalp, Trinayan Baruah, Shlesh Tiwari, and S. Sankar Ganesh. Intelligent classification of electronic music. 2014 IEEE International Symposium on Signal Processing and Information Technology, ISSPIT 2014, pages 31–35, 2015.
- [27] Craig Strachan. Industry , Ideology , Aesthetics and Micro Independent Record Labels in the UK for the degree of Doctor in Philosophy. (March):1–398, 2003.
- [28] Julián Urbano, Markus Schedl, and Xavier Serra. Evaluation in music information retrieval. Journal of Intelligent Information Systems, 2013.
- [29] Kris West, Stephen Cox, and Paul Lamere. Incorporating machine-learning into music similarity estimation. Proceedings of the ACM International Multimedia Conference and Exhibition, pages 89–96, 2006.
- [30] B. Whitman and S. Lawrence. Inferring descriptions and similarity for music from community metadata. Proceedings of the 2002 International Computer Music Conference, (March), 2002.
- [31] Minz Won, Andres Ferraro, Dmitry Bogdanov, and Xavier Serra. Evaluation of CNN-based Automatic Music Tagging Models. 2020.

- [32] Changsheng Xu, Namunu C. Maddage, Xi Shao, Fang Cao, and Qi Tian. Musical genre classification using support vector machines. ICASSP, IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing - Proceedings, 5:429–432, 2003.
- [33] Yibin Zhong and Jie Zhou. A study on content-based music classification. Proceedings - 7th International Symposium on Signal Processing and Its Applications, ISSPA 2003, 2:113–116, 2003.